

Non linear model control for industrial robots

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Abstract—In this article, the results of a nonlinear model predictive controller used to generate optimized trajectories for an omnidirectional industrial robot equipped with a spraying unit is presented. Results are provided for various trajectories along with consideration of controller performance.

Index Terms—service robotics, path planner, nonlinear predictive control, industrial robots, autonomous navigation

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the past few years, more and more companies have been trying to find new and innovative methods to integrate robotic solutions into their manufacturing line to improve their processes and increase their products quality. However, despite these efforts, the optimization of manufacturing processes is currently only partially addressed using industrial mobile robots. With the growing demand for goods coming mainly from online orders, the logistics industry is surely facing a difficult challenge focusing the attention on the efficiency of logistics. A new and modern concept of intelligent warehouses is gaining importance and is based on a series of automation tasks that are typically based on artificial intelligence (AI) technology, providing high automation, low labor cost and very high efficiency. It is based on intelligent warehouses, is based on a standardized system of tasks that typically depend on artificial intelligence technology (AI), has low labor costs and can provide very high automation, low labor costs, and high efficiency. In this context, industrial research is orienting its efforts to the development of machinery and methods that can have an influence on production methodologies and improve the retrieval of goods following the palletization process [1][2]. These innovations make it possible to benefit from a series of advantages, including the possibility of creating a well-defined logistic flow with a fixed path [3], increasingly automated and interconnected production models and greater flexibility [4], all while rationalizing costs and optimizing performance. This research work aims to provide results on the performance obtained by a non-linear model predictive control used to plan trajectories for an omnidirectional mobile robot able to automatically mark lines on the floor of wide exhibition halls in order to outline the area where each stand should be placed by saving time, human efforts and environmentally friendly paints.

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II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. The omnidirectional robot

The omnidirectional vehicle used for this research, named Omnibot, is shown in 1. Omnibot is based on a rectangular plan having an overall length and width of, respectively, $b = 1012$ mm and $a = 1038$ mm to provide a large supporting base. It is equipped with four assemblies made up of a mecanum wheel (5), a gearbox with reduction ratio $i = 30$, a 500 W brushed DC motor up to 3000 rpm and an optical encoder with 1024 pulses used in order to provide an efficient and robust locomotion system [5]. The motors are controlled

Fig. 1. The Omnidirectional platform with the spraying unit

by a total of four drivers featuring a high-performance 32-bit microcomputer and quadrature encoder inputs to perform advanced motion control algorithms in both open-loop and closed-loop modes for speed and position. In order to enable the vehicle to provide an extended working autonomy, a 24 VDC 200 Ah AGM battery pack (8) has been installed to allow a maximum output power of 4.8 kW protected by a 350 A battery isolator switch based on a high-load solenoid. Each mecanum wheel has a vertical load capacity of 250 kg and the metal frame of the robot has a total payload of 1000 kg to allow the use of large and heavy equipment in industrial environments. The robot has been completely custom built starting from CAD design, and all the parts have been manufactured by using laser cut and bending machines. The vehicle uses an airless spraying system powered by an hydraulic pump (2), commanded by a motor driver (6), that sucks out the paint stored in two upper tanks (1) and feeds it to a bottom nozzle (4) usually placed 25 cm away from the floor, even if its height can be adjusted using the positioning

holes available on the nozzle support. Finally, an internal 12 VDC air compressor (3) is used to enable or disable the nozzle. All the system can be powered on and off by using the main control panel (7), which also provides an emergency switch and a series of power connectors to plug additional devices. Table I reports the main mechanical specifications for the presented omnidirectional platform. It worth to mention that an omnidirectional platform has been selected over other configurations like tank steering because mecanum wheels minimize the slipping effect on flat surfaces as well as the vertical vibrations on the frame [6].

TABLE I
OMNIBOT MAIN TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS

Omnibot specifications	Value
Number of motors	4
Overall dimensions	1012×1038mm
Maximum velocity (any direction)	1 m/s
Maximum Payload	1000 kg
Output power	4800 W
Vehicle weight	200 kg

B. The robot dynamic model

Over the years, the controls used in robotics systems have dramatically changed to allow for more complex and dynamic non-linear actions. Model predictive control (MPC) solves an optimization problem at each time step to find the optimal control action that drives the predicted plant output to the desired reference as close as possible [7][8]. MPC controller is a more advanced method of process control with the ability to deal with the constraints used for MIMO systems (Multiple Inputs, Multiple Outputs) compared with PID controller that has no knowledge about the constraints. A MPC can be considered as a multi-variable control algorithm that relies on an internal dynamic model of the process, a cost function J over the receding horizon [9] which is a time window for the prediction and an optimization algorithm minimizing the cost function J using the control inputs.

$$J = \sum_{i=1}^N w_{x_i} (r_i - x_i)^2 + \sum_{i=1}^N w_{u_i} \Delta u_i^2 \quad (1)$$

where J is the cost function, x_i are the controlled variables or system states, r_i are the robot reference variables, u_i are the inputs expected by the robot or the manipulated variables, w_{x_i} and w_{u_i} are the weight coefficients chosen according to the requirements and are relative to x_i and u_i , respectively. The above cost function J minimizes the error from a reference trajectory and the jerk caused by drastic deviations in the inputs.

MPC receives the current states of the robot and simulates a number of combinations of control inputs for time from k to $k + p$ where p is related to the sample time. Among several possibilities, MPC selects the best set of inputs which minimizes the cost function J . Only the first step of this control strategy is implemented, then the system state is

sampled again and the calculations are repeated starting from the new current state $k+1$ up to $k+1+p$ with a new control and a new predicted state path. The prediction horizon continues to move forward with the same duration p , and for this reason MPC is also called receding horizon control (RHC).

C. 2.2 Non-linear predictive model control (NMPC)

In general, MPC is the most standard advanced control method used in process industries, especially for those systems that can be adequately represented with a linear model. The growing use of this algorithm is justified by its ability to manage large-scale multi-variable processes with tens or hundreds of inputs and states that must satisfy physical and operational constraints. The operating principle of the MPC algorithm relies on the formulation and the solution of a numerical optimization problem corresponding to an optimal control problem with a finite time horizon p at each sampling instant k . Since the system state is updated during each sampling period, the receding horizon approach must be adopted, so a new optimization problem must be solved at each sampling interval. Linear models can be handled using a large variety of numerical and software methods since the MPC problem in those cases is typically a quadratic or linear program, which is known to be convex and so easily to be solved. However, mobile robots kinematic models are non-linear affine systems constrained by velocity and acceleration limits. The non-linear model predictive control (NMPC) seems to be able to provide the possibility to operate with non-linear system. The first step is to formulate a non-linear optimal control problem that is then transformed into a constrained non-linear programming (NLP) problem by using a discretization scheme over a prediction horizon and by repeatedly solving this problem online. By considering a general nonlinear system:

$$\dot{x}(t) = f(x(t), u(t)), \quad x(0) = x_0, \quad y = h(x(t), u(t)) \quad (2)$$

described by the following inputs and state constraints:

$$u(t) \in \mathcal{U}, \quad x(t) \in \mathcal{X}, \quad \forall t \geq 0 \quad (3)$$

where $x(t)$ is the state of the system and $u(t)$ is the input applied to it. The set of possible inputs is denoted by \mathcal{U} , while the set of possible states is indicated by \mathcal{X} and the set of initial conditions is \mathcal{X}_0 . In NMPC, the feedback is defined by the repeated solution of an optimal control problem in an open loop. The optimal open-loop control problem to be solved is often formulated as:

$$\min_{\bar{u}} J(\bar{x}(\bullet), \bar{u}(\bullet)) \quad (4)$$

with:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\bar{x}}(\tau) &= f(\bar{x}(\tau), \bar{u}(\tau)), \quad \bar{x}(t) = x(t), \\ \bar{u}(\tau) &\in \mathcal{U}, \quad \tau \in [t, t + T_p], \\ \bar{x}(\tau) &\in \mathcal{X}, \quad \tau \in [t, t + T_p], \\ \bar{x}(t + T_p) &\in \mathcal{E} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where the cost function J is defined over the prediction horizon T_p as:

$$J(x(\bullet), u(\bullet)) = \int_t^{t+T_p} F(x(\tau), u(\tau)) d\tau + E(x(t+T_p)) \quad (6)$$

with F that is a stage cost function and E is defined as terminal penalty that typically penalizes the distance of the last predicted state from the origin [10]. The optimal value function can be described as follows:

$$V(x(t)) = J(x(\bullet; x(t), \bar{u}^*(\bullet; x(t))), \bar{u}^*(\bullet; x(t))) \quad (7)$$

plays a crucial role in NMPC stability considerations. One of the main reasons connected to the success of this non-linear controller is its ability to explicitly take into account the constraints which can be defined both for the set of inputs (saturation constraints) and for the controlled variables y (i.e. to limit the overshoot value or to try to prevent non-minimal phase behaviors). All states are measured with a fixed sampling time T_s and their values are provided to the NMPC algorithm with the same sampling to obtain a prediction of the system. The control law at any time calculates a prediction of the states and of the outputs on an interval $[t, t+T_p]$ where T_p represents the prediction horizon. Then, the NMPC evaluates the expected output of the system according to the initial state of that prediction interval $x(t)$, and the input for a specific instant of time of that interval. To simplify the calculation, it can be assumed that the input changes only for a time fraction of the prediction horizon also called the control horizon, after which the input value remains constant. Both T_p and T_C are integer multiples of the sampling time T_S while $u(t)$ is an open-loop input since it no longer depends on the initial state. The main purpose of the controller is to generate at each sampling time a prediction-based input that minimizes the cost function J . The specification of NMPC control functionality and dynamic performance is essentially provided by the cost function and the constraints of the system. The optimization problem consists of minimizing at each sampling instant the squared-weighted norm of the tracking error, over a finite time interval. The other contributions in the cost function take into account the final tracking error and how the algorithm manages the trade-off between performance and command activity.

III. NUMERIC RESULTS

In order to test the performance of the NMPC over the dynamic model of the robot, MATLAB has been used since it allows matrix manipulations, plotting of functions and data, implementation of algorithms, creation of user interfaces, and interfacing with programs written in other languages; in particular, it provides a non-linear MPC function to calculate control actions at each control interval using a combination of model-based prediction and constrained optimization. A total of ten simulation tests has been performed to arrive at the best combination of parameters, i.e. the values of the constraints and weights relating to the manipulable variables, the weights relating to the output variables, that allows the robot to follow the desired trajectory. For each simulation case,

the RMS (Root Mean Square) value was calculated to quantify the deviation or deviation between the points of the desired trajectory and those belonging to the real trajectory. Left side of Figure 2 shows the reference trajectory, in red, and the trajectory followed by the robot, in blue, with the robot starting from the upper left corner moving from left to right, while, on the right it is possible to see in detail the error between the two trajectories close to the bottom angle while Figure 4 shows the trend of the velocity for each mecanum wheel; it is interesting to note that the graphs are divided in three main regions corresponding to the first horizontal trajectory from $t = 0$ to $t = 110$, the second vertical line with $t = 110$ to $t = 240$ and the last horizontal trajectory from $t = 240$ to $t = 360$. Moreover, the controller commands the robot to follow a circular trajectory by changing the velocity on the left wheels while reversing the spinning direction on the right ones. Figures 3 and 5 shows the results obtained by running the NMPC by reducing the horizon prediction time and control. In this case, the trajectory followed by the robot is affected by a greater deviation from the reference path.

Fig. 2. Results from a simulation with the NMPC algorithm

Fig. 3. Results obtained using a reduced prediction time

The RMS values obtained during three of the ten simulations equal to 0.1530, 0.2205 and 0.4011 as reported in Table II.

The best result with the lowest RMS value is obtained during Test 1 by setting to $W_v = 25$ the weight for the manipulated variables, $W_{vr} = 1$ the weight for the manipulated variables rate and $W_{vo} = 100$ for the output variables with a prediction horizon set to 15 time samples and a control horizon

Fig. 4. Wheel angular velocities with NMPC

Fig. 5. Wheel angular velocities with reduced prediction time

TABLE II
RMS VALUES FOR THREE SIMULATION TESTS

Tests	RMS
1	0.1530
2	0.2205
3	0.4011

equal to 5. Using weight values greater than the previous ones leads to a less accurate path following; the same happens if both the prediction and the control horizon are reduced.

Fig. 6. Comparison between reference and real trajectory on a curved path

The controller has been tested also on more complex paths like the curved trajectory showed in Figure 6 where it can be observed how the robot's blue trajectory is very close to the reference one except for the area $-1 < x < 1$ where the curve is tighter.

IV. 4. CONCLUSIONS

This research aimed to evaluate the performance obtained by applying nonlinear model predictive control to an omnidirectional mobile robot. Results obtained from various trajectories are presented, as well as their RMS values, as a comparison tool to assess controller effectiveness by taking the results obtained. Future work should focus on direct application of this controller to robots to test their performance in real world environments.

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